

Investigating the Major Challenges that Encountered EFL Learners in the Implementation of Intercultural-Oriented Task-Based Instruction on Improving Oral Skills at the College Level.

Abstract

The main objective of this study was to investigate the major challenges encountered by EFL learners in the implementation of Intercultural Communication Oriented Task-Based Language Instruction in improving their oral skills at the college level. The researcher was employed a descriptive survey design by developing a questionnaire comprising 27 items and administered in EFL settings. All students in Jimma College were the population of the study, and data were collected from 28 students of the same department of English language as sample respondents. Then, the collected data was analysed using the quantitative method. The result of the study indicated that among others, lack of teachers' readiness to implement cultural-oriented activities during oral skill practices; lack of experiences in designing intercultural oriented tasks; lack of commitment so as to practicing oral skills; implementing poor teaching methods; lack of evaluating oral performance through oral presentations and on the student's side, students' lack of prior knowledge on such task, poor prior exposure to oral tasks, lack of basic English skills, fear of making mistakes, and poor vocabulary knowledge were critical challenges. Finally, a few recommendations point forwarded for educational planners and textbook writers, supervisors, and English language teachers.

Key words: Intercultural Contact, Culture-oriented tasks, Socialization, Culture-teaching, oral skills, culture-learning

1. Introduction

English is that the language that distended breaking the barriers of colour, race, and belief that have continued to unfold everywhere on the planet (Willis, 2007). As a result, it has become the language of affairs. English has become the language that links the planet all at once. It is the medium through that technological, social, political, and cultural information has been transmitted.

Intercultural contact and communication have allegedly inflated within the context of globalization. Each terms squire measure, however, very little clear, evoke a number of associations, and carry ideologic baggage (Karin Zotazmann ,2007).FL learning should transcend the extent of acquiring grammatical rules; FL learners got to skills to use the target language within the situated context. It is impossible to show a language without its culture for “culture is that the necessary context for language use.” Some FL communication situation examples demonstrated that the cultural contents of the target culture(s) needed to be integrated into FL teaching for cultural contexts to avoid misunderstanding even when people are using correct FL linguistic forms.

The fact that the intercultural-oriented competence is one of the key competencies within the twenty-first century, thus, it is united that one in all the last word goals in language coaching programs is to teach learners to become intercultural speakers who can deal with linguistic and cultural complexity and take part in multi-cultural situations. Nevertheless, in the reality of English education in Ethiopia, most of the English language training programs lack the integration of cultural content into their curriculum and English language users are to some extent incapable of using English appropriately and effectively when communicating with others from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds due to lack of awareness of the cultural difference.

Current Literature on English Language Teaching (ELT) criticizes the transfer of Communicative instruction (CI) from Western English-speaking countries to alternative development contexts. This transfer is seen as problematic since pedagogy introduced from abroad conflicts with the social, cultural, and physical conditions of the recipient countries. However, abandoning CLT within the English classrooms in countries like Vietnam or China looks to not a practical life, on the condition that the ultimate goal of English teaching in these countries is to assist learners to acquire a decent operating command of English. Therefore,

seems to be a changed version of CLT, created acceptable to the native condition. This article defines the theoretical essentials of CLT and characterizes the issues that commonly arise when CLT theory is put into practice, aiming to offer suggestions to help EFL teachers in non-Western EFL settings develop appropriate CLT practices for their classrooms (Hiep, 2005).

Language is taken in to account because the information of synchronic linguistics, consisting of syntax, accidence, and phonemics, that encompasses information of formal rules or operations that care for abstract linguistic classes, as an example, verb and noun, and phrases (Farid, 2017). The main of learning as far off foreign language is to find out to speak within in the target language, to find out learn the customs and traditions of the community, and to push one's study and work. Communicative ability is non-heritable through the socialization of the speaker. A person, from an ignorant individual to a social member, must learn the knowledge, skill, and conversation so as to adjust himself to society and qualify himself as a social member.

This method is thought because the socialization of a person and it goes throughout a man's life. This is true not solely to one's linguistic communication however additionally to his learning a distant language, as a social product, totally embodies the culture of its community and is closely associated with to the culture of the speck community. Intercultural human activity suggests that human activity among people that come back from several and varied cultures through face to face interaction. For foreign language educators, to develop the learner's intercultural communication competency is to understand the way to teach foreign culture. Culture teaching in foreign language teaching is a question countered by language teachers throughout all universities and colleges in the world (Sun, 2013).

To sum up, Ethiopian universities or colleges are characterized by constituting students from different cultural backgrounds, experiences, and cultural backgrounds. However, the essence and the nature of communication among such culturally diverse students have not been investigated through the methodologies of intercultural communication. Thus, this study intends to analyse the system of intercultural communication among college students in Jimma teachers' education.

2. Review of Literature

2.1. Conceptual Framework

The main purpose of this study is to have a detailed investigation about if there are major challenges or barriers encountered by EFL learners' in the implementation of intercultural communication- oriented TBLI in improving EFL learner's oral skills at the college level. Based on the above- related literature review and concepts the conceptual framework for this study is developed.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

2.2. Theoretical Framework

2.3. The need for CLT

With the importance of English within the world nowadays and also the demand to show learners an operating command of English to satisfy numerous communicative wants in their life, EFL educators in various countries have felt associate degree urge to be told the most recent and best ways of teaching. For instance, lectures of English acknowledge that ancient pedagogy, give emphasis to the acquisition of language rules and words instead of communicative competency, and don't light the wants of English learning in associate degree era of integration and economic process. Since the first nineteen, therefore, CLT has quickly gained quality in the world.

Universities and Colleges haven't solely inspired lectures of English to attend workshops and seminars on CLT given by foreign academic within the country however have conjointly sent their teaching employees abroad.

2.4. Creating genuine communication

In essence, CLT theory holds that learning takes place through real communication. Proposes that communication is probably going occur within the English Language classrooms when:-

- (1) A major quantity of pair work and cluster work is conducted;
 - (2) Authentic language input in real-life context is provided;
 - (3) Students acquire measure inspired to supply language for real, significant communication; and
 - (4) Tasks are accompanied to organize to students for actual language use outside the classroom.
- Also, notes that it's vital "to assist tiny cluster and paired activities during which students have opportunities to cooperate. The actions themselves typically interact often engage students' in communicative tasks like filling information gaps using authentic materials" (Hiep, 2005).

2.5.The Relationship between Language and Culture

The relationship between language and culture is dynamic. Firstly, language is a crucial part of the culture. It is the first vehicle by that a culture transmits its beliefs, values, and norms. Secondly, language is influenced by culture. Language is one in all the foremost most necessary carriers of culture and reflects the latter. If there is no language, culture would not be legendary. On the one hand, culture is that the basis and one in all the foremost necessary attributes of language and exerts excessive impact on the latter. If there is no culture, language are like water while not a supply or a tree without roots(Li Sun ,2013).

2.6.The Relationship between Culture and Foreign Language Teaching

They typically use linguistic communication patterns or rules in learning the target language, which ends up in errors or inappropriate forms within the target language. This can

be known as negative transfer, conjointly referred to as interference. Language is inextricably certain up with culture. Cultural values square measure each mirrored by and carried through language. Consequently, it's inevitable that the manner of thinking and expressing influenced by the native culture are unconsciously transferred to the target language throughout intercultural communication.

That is the cultural transfer. As a matter of fact, the most difficult thing for language learners to deal with in their study of the foreign language is not the linguistic forms or grammar, but the cultural difference. In the process of cognition of the world, people always store the schemata into their brain, schemata can be compared to an immense system of files in one's brain, where you can classify and store your brain and individual knowledge and experience(Sun, 2013).

2.7.Intercultural Communication

Effective intercultural communication happens once that means is each shared and created. Language and culture area unit connected, therein in that culture shapes language use and language conveys cultural meanings. While not shared assumptions, values, and beliefs, communication may be problematic or awkward, as interlocutors have to be compelled to overcome each psychological feature cognitive and effective barriers. Stereotyping, ethnocentrism, prejudice, discrimination, and cultural distance area unit some factors which will contribute to intercultural miscommunication. Lacking these skills, people from completely different cultures can risk misunderstanding each other, though they are fluent speakers of a similar language. An intercultural method to language teaching maintenances pupils in attaining cultural skills as they progress ability in the old-fashioned four skills (reading, writing, listening, and speaking).

2.8.Intercultural Competence

Intercultural ability is that the “ability to assume and act in applicable ways that folks from different cultures. This encompasses (a) the capability to acknowledge, experience, and address cultural variations in intercultural circumstances and (b) the mandatory information of socio-cultural contexts to affect issues which will arise. It is helpful to form a distinction between culture-specific understanding (knowing regarding aspects a specific culture) over time, a

number of different cultural value orientations have been proposed as a means of understanding culture in a more general way (Bickley, 2014).

2.9. Language, culture, and communication

Both language and culture have a function of communication because they both carry meanings. On the one hand, language carries syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic meanings for language users to communicate. In order to communicate successfully across languages and cultures, one must understand culturally different forms of interaction and people's values and think. Sometimes linguistically correct sentences could cause misunderstanding or confusion when they are in a different cultural context (Hsin, 2007).

2.10. Communicative language teaching: implications for the communicative classrooms

In terms of learning, it is normally accepted that we need to differentiate between knowing various grammatical rules and being able to use the rules effectively and appropriately when communicating. A teacher who is well-informed about the functional view of language and adopts a communicative approach to language teaching would hold the principle that the improvement of communicative language ability is the purpose of classroom learning.

Therefore, a tactful teacher would emphasize on communicative apply with in language classrooms. The communicative practices within the CLT area unit considered by some principles. Firstly, the teacher can produce activities that facilitate real communication motivating students to find out. As an example, the up-to-date teacher will produce a conducive teaching learning classroom setting during which interaction between one student and another happens. Next, the teacher can hold task principle, which implies that he will encourage learning by making classroom activities during which language is employed to conduct meaningful tasks suggests that with specific task conditions learners won't simply expose their language hypotheses, however suppose seriously regarding them and use the language yet (Farid, 2017).

2.11. Communicative language teaching

CLT doesn't take to any specific theory of learning; the practices related to it imply many underlying theoretical principles that they describe as follows:

1. The communication principle: Activities that involve real communication promote learning.
2. The task principle: Activities within which language is employed for resounding significant out meaningful tasks promote learning.
3. The significance principle: Language is that significant to the learner supports the training method (Rubio et.al, 2004).

3. General Objectives

The general objective of the study was to investigate the major challenges or barriers that encountered EFL learners in the implementation of Intercultural Communication Oriented Task-Based language Instruction in Improving EFL learners' oral skill at college level. Specifically, the study attempts to answer the following basic research questions

4. Research Questions

1. Is there major barriers or challenges encountered in the implementation of the intercultural-communication oriented task-based language instruction that intends to improve college- level EFL students' oral skills?
2. Is there major barriers or challenges related to teachers, students, and resources encountered in the implementation of the intercultural communication- oriented task -based language instruction that intends to improve college- level EFL students' oral skills?

3. Material and Methods

3.1. Research Design

The major aim of this study was to investigate the challenges encountered EFL learners in the implementation of intercultural oriented task based instruction that intends to improve their oral skills at college level. The study employed descriptive survey research design. Descriptive research design enables the researcher to identify some of major problems in relation to teacher, students, and resources related challenges.

3.2. Study Setting

The study was conducted in Jimma City College of teachers' education which is found 346 km far away from Addis Ababa which is the capital city of Ethiopia.

3.3. Participants

The subjects were only one group (28) TEFL majors who had to take the College English Spoken course instructed by the present teachers. The choice of the sample of the study was based on available sampling techniques. The subjects consisted of 17 (60%) males and 11(40%) females. Their average age was between 18-25 years old. The present researcher was purposively selecting the college.

3.4. Instruments of data collection

The current study used one questionnaire that contained of on scale to quantitatively identify the major challenges that encountered EFL learners in the implementation of intercultural oriented task-based language instruction that intends to improve their oral skill at college level. The questionnaire comprised three parts: Part I explained the challenges related to teachers. Part II mainly focus on challenges related to learners and the last part III focus on challenges related to resources and environmental challenges which is totally 27-item and 5-Likert scale

3.5. Procedures of data collection

The researcher used a series of data gathering producers. The Questionnaire consists set of open and closed-ended questions to be distributed to only students. Jimma College of teachers education was only one group of English major students. Based on the objective of the study the researcher selected the sample students through available sampling and purposive sampling was used for the college. Then, the prepared questionnaire was spread for the sample subjects for Jimma College of teacher education. Before the delivery of the data gathering tools, the researcher consulted with advisors. Then, the questionnaires were distributed to the sample selected students.

3.6. Data processing and Analysis

After collecting the data, the researcher processed them by using statistical computation which was used to analyse the data from one group using frequency and % respectively.

7. Findings and Discussion

Table 1: Results Shows teacher related challenges

Variables	S. Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	S. agree
The teacher's lack of knowledge and experience in preparing intercultural communication based tasks that intend to develop learners' oral skills	3(10.7%)	6(21.4%)	4(14.3%)	10(35.7%)	5(17.9%)
Lack of appropriately prepared authentic intercultural oriented learning material for meeting the demands of effective interaction during spoken lessons	3(10.7%)	6(21.4%)	5(17.9%)	8(28.6%)	6(21.4%)
Lack of using new or innovative teaching techniques during the Oral lessons offered	2(7.1%)	3(10.7%)	5(17.9%)	15(53.6%)	3(10.7%)
Use of teacher-cantered teaching methods during the speaking Lessons	2(7.1%)	5(17.9%)	6(21.4%)	11(39.3%)	4(14.3%)
Lack of various intercultural communication oriented task based activities in the spoken lessons	1(3.6%)	6(21.4%)	4(14.3%)	10(35.7%)	7(25.0%)
Failure in giving clear instruction	4(14.3%)	5(17.9%)	3(10.7%)	11(39.3%)	5(17.9%)
Lack of enough guide and support to learners when they face problems in doing intercultural communication oriented task based speaking activities	3(10.7%)	6(21.4%)	6(21.4%)	9(32.1%)	4(14.3%)
Use of difficult English in the speaking instruction	7(25.0%)	5(17.9%)	5(17.9%)	7(25.0%)	4(14.3%)

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Lack of encouraging learners to take part in the speaking tasks	3(10.7%)	7(25.0%)	4(14.3%)	9(32.1%)	5(17.9%)
Lack of good or effective classrooms management	3(10.7%)	6(21.4%)	1(3.6%)	13(46.4%)	5(17.9%)
No objectives set for the spoken lesson	4(14.3%)	6(21.4%)	7(25.0%)	8(28.6%)	3(10.7%)

Table 1 presents students' responses regarding teachers' related challenges in the implementation of the intercultural-oriented task-based instruction that intends to improve EFL learners' oral skills. As can be seen in item 1, (Table 1), students were asked if there are challenges or barriers related to teachers' lack of knowledge and experience in preparing intercultural communication- based tasks that intend to develop learners' oral skills or not. In responding to this item, as it can be seen from the table above, the respondents 3 (10.7%), 6 (21.4%), 4(14.3), 10(35.7), and 5(17.9) confirmed that strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree respectively. From the above data analysis simply conclude that there were major challenges or barriers related to teachers' lack of knowledge and experience in preparing intercultural communication -based tasks that intend to develop learners' oral skills in language classrooms.

Item 2, students were asked whether or not teachers lack appropriately prepared or adopted authentic intercultural oriented learning material for meeting the demands of effective interaction in the Spoken language classroom students should develop strategies for making sense of what they speak, engage in the speaking process, and develop the ability to communicate effectively in language classrooms. Accordingly, the majority of the participants 6 (21.4%), and 8 (28.6%) them confirmed disagree agree, and agree respectively. Therefore, the given response showed us teachers should develop appropriately prepared or adopted authentic intercultural oriented learning material for meeting the demands of effective interaction in the Spoken language classroom.

Item 3, students were asked whether the lack of using new or innovative teaching techniques during the Oral lessons offered was teachers' related challenges or not. Accordingly, the respondents responded that 2 (7.1%) strongly disagree , 3 (10.7%)disagree ,5(17.5%)

neutral,15(53.6%) agree ,and the rest of 3(10.7%) strongly agree respectively. Therefore, the respondent's responses indicated that teachers' lack of using new or innovative teaching techniques during the Oral lessons offered was the major challenge in the implementation of intercultural- oriented task- based that intends to improve EFL learners' oral skills in the language classrooms.

Item 4: students were asked whether the use of teacher-cantered teaching methods during the speaking Lessons was the major challenge or not. Thus, the above table shows that 2 (7.1%) strongly disagree,5(17.9%)disagree ,6(21.4%), neutral,11(39.3%)agree, and the rest of the 4(14.3%) of the respondents confirmed strongly agree respectively. Therefore, the confirmed result indicated that using teacher-cantered teaching methods during the speaking Lessons was the major challenge in the implementation of the intercultural oriented task-based that intends to improve student's oral skills.

Item 5 students were asked whether teachers lack various intercultural communication-oriented task-based activities in the spoken lessons given tasks and activities are difficult for them while they learn an oral skills or not. Thus, the majority of the respondent 10 (35.5%) and 7 (25%) confirmed agree and strongly agree respectively. On the other hand, a small number of respondents 1 (3.6%) and 4(14.5) confirmed strongly disagree and neutral with the statements. Nevertheless, the obtained result implies that the majority of the respondent's response falls under categories of agreeing and strongly agree on which mean that difficulties of the tasks/ activities are might be due to the teachers lack various intercultural communication-oriented task-based activities in the spoken lessons.

Item 6, 7, 8,9,10, and 11 students were asked teachers failure in giving clear instruction, lack of enough guide and support to learners when they face problems in doing the intercultural communication-oriented task-based speaking activities, use of difficult English in the speaking instruction, lack of encouraging learners to take part in the speaking tasks, lack of good or effective classrooms management, and no objectives set for spoken lessons. Regarding to those items, the majority of the respondents11 (39.3%) agree , 9 (32.1%) agree ,7(25%) agree ,9(32.1%)agree ,13(46.4%) agree , 8(28.6%) agree respectively. Therefore, this result showed us ELT teachers do not use different teaching methods in order to improve EFL oral skills during the implementation of intercultural -oriented task- based instruction.

Table 2: Questionnaire Results Shows trainees related challenges

Variables	S. Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	S. Agree
Lack background or prior knowledge and experiences of doing Such speaking or oral tasks at lower learning levels	5(17.9%)	4(14.3%)	3(10.7%)	8(28.6%)	8(28.6%)
Lack basic English language skills for doing intercultural communication-oriented task-based that intends to improve Speaking activities	3(10.7%)	3(10.7%)	5(17.9%)	10(35.7%)	7(25.0%)
Fear of making mistakes, losing face, criticism, and my Shyness during task-based speaking instruction	2(7.1%)	3(10.7%)	4(14.3%)	14(50.0%)	5(17.9%)
Poor vocabulary Knowledge	4(14.3%)	6(21.4%)	6(21.4%)	9(32.1%)	3(10.7%)
Lack motivation to learn through such tasks that were used in the oral lessons	3(10.7%)	4(14.3%)	7(25.0%)	9(32.1%)	5(17.9%)
I prefer to use my mother tongue during English speaking lessons	3(10.7%)	4(14.3%)	4(14.3%)	12(42.9%)	5(17.9%)
Lack of confidence in taking part in the intercultural communication -oriented task- based English Spoken lessons	3(10.7%)	4(14.3%)	6(21.4%)	12(42.9%)	3(10.7%)
Speaking in English is difficult for me	2(7.1%)	7(25.0%)	3(10.7%)	9(32.1%)	7(25.0%)
Hating interactive pair or group works during the spoken lessons	2(7.1%)	7(25.0%)	2(7.1%)	12(42.9%)	5(17.9%)

Nine items were designed and delivered for the sample respondents of students and data were collected and analysed in the above table 2 focusing on the major challenges or barriers related to trainees in the implementation of intercultural-oriented-task based instruction in language classrooms. Item 1, students were asked if the student's lack background or prior knowledge and experiences of doing such speaking or oral tasks at lower learning levels. Accordingly, the majority of the respondents 5 (17.9%) strongly disagree, 4 (14.3%) disagree, 3(10.7%) neutral, 8(28.6%) agree and 8(28.6%) replied strongly disagree to the statements. Hence the majority of responses obtained fall under the categories of agreeing, and strongly agrees respectively. Thus, the student's lack of background or prior knowledge and experiences of doing Such speaking or oral tasks at lower learning levels were the serious problem that hinder them during the implementation of the intercultural -oriented task-based instruction.

Item 2, students were asked whether lack basic English language skills for doing the intercultural communication -oriented task- based that intends to improve their Speaking skill or not. Accordingly, the obtained results indicated that 3(10.7%) strongly disagree, 3(10.7%) disagree, 5(17.9%) neutral, 10(35.7%) agree, and 7(25%) strongly agree respectively. Therefore, this result showed us students lack basic English language skills for doing the intercultural communication- oriented task- based was the major challenges related to the trainees.

Besides this, fear of making mistakes, losing face, criticism, and may Shyness during task-based speaking instruction 14(50.0%), Poor vocabulary Knowledge 9(32.1%), Lack of motivation to learn through such tasks that were used in the oral lessons 9(32.1%), prefer to use their mother tongue during English speaking lessons 12(42.9%), Lack of confidence in taking part in the intercultural communication- oriented task -based English spoken lessons 12(42.9%), Speaking in English is difficult for me 9(32.1%) and hating interactive pair or group works during the spoken lessons 12(42.9%) were trainees related challenges respectively.

Table 3: Questionnaire Results Shows learning resource and environmental related challenges

Variables	S. Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	S. Agree
Enough time is not given for the teaching and learning intercultural communication oriented-tasks that intend to promote student's Spoken skills	2(7.1%)	3(10.7%)	2(7.1%)	12(42.9%)	9(32.1%)
Lack of appropriate teaching aids to facilitate the English speaking lessons	2(7.1%)	5(17.9%)	5(17.9%)	11(39.3%)	5(17.9%)
Lack of adequate or enough teaching aids to facilitate the English speaking lessons	1(3.6%)	6(21.4%)	5(17.9%)	11(39.3%)	5(17.9%)
The sitting arrangements are not convenient for interactive group works that facilitate learners English speaking skills	4(14.3%)	9(32.1%)	5(17.9%)	6(21.4%)	4(14.3%)
English language is not spoken outside classrooms	2(7.1%)	1(3.6%)	4(14.3%)	12(42.9%)	9(32.1%)
Shortage of time allotted to different task- based activities to Promote learners' oral skills development	1(3.6%)	4(14.3%)	2(7.1%)	18(64.3%)	3(10.7%)
The classroom surrounding is noisy	10(35.7%)	10(35.7%)	2(7.1%)	5(17.9%)	1(3.6%)

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Seven items were designed and delivered for the sample respondents of students whether learning resource and environmental-related challenges were the major challenges were encountered in the implementation of intercultural -oriented task- based or not. The respondents revealed that enough time is not given for the teaching and learning intercultural communication - oriented tasks that intend to promote student’s Spoken skills 12(42.9%), lack of appropriate teaching aids to facilitate the English speaking lessons 11(39.3%), lack of adequate or enough teaching aids to facilitate the English speaking lessons 11(39.3%), the sitting arrangements (or, the seats) are not convenient for interactive group works that facilitate learners English speaking skills 6(21.4%) and English language is not spoken outside classrooms 12(42.9%) respectively. Above half of the respondents, 18(64.3%) agree on the shortage of time allotted to different task-based activities to Promote learners’ oral skills development. Finally, most of the respondents strongly disagree 10(35.7%) on that the classroom surrounding is noisy.

8. Analysis and Discussions of Findings

The leading source of challenge, according to the consensus point of the majority of the respondents’ views, learner related challenges, rated by cumulative average mean 3.94, followed by the next serious challenge which was resources and environmental related one, rated by cumulative average mean 3.72 and finally came teacher related challenge, rated by cumulative average mean 3.66 respectively.

Among others, the most perturbing challenges detailed in the learner related challenges were:

- Lack basic English language skills for doing intercultural communication oriented task based that intends to improve Speaking activities;
- Lack background or prior knowledge and experiences of doing such speaking or oral tasks at lower learning levels; and
- Fear of making mistakes, losing face, criticism, and shyness during task-based speaking instructions were the compelling ones.

Regarding the teacher related challenges:

- Lack of various intercultural communication oriented task based activities in the spoken lessons;
- Use of teacher-centered teaching methods during the speaking lessons;
- Lack of enough guide and support to learners when they face problems in doing intercultural communication oriented task based speaking activities were the most perturbing challenges.

The most serious resource and environmental related challenges were:

- Lack of encouraging climate that sufficiently exposes students to use English language outside classrooms;
- Shortage of time allotted to different task based activities to promote learners' oral skills development;
- Enough time is not given for the teaching and learning intercultural communication oriented tasks that intend to promote student's Spoken skills.

9. Conclusion and Recommendation

The results of this investigation show that culture-based tasks offer several benefits to language classes. It can be useful in developing linguistic knowledge, and, if duly motivated, extend students' oral skill proficiency. Needless to say, culture-based activity learning/ teaching is an essential supplement for language teaching, which enables students to experience pleasure from language learning (Lili Dai, 2011).

The learning of target-language culture-related content can improve students' understanding of the target language, enrich their ability to understanding. Obviously learning target-language culture can reinforce students' understanding of the world and cultivate their understanding, and experiences. Besides, effective teaching methodology of integrating culture-based tasks with oral skill both EFL learners have a positive attitude toward relationship and importance of teaching oral skill with culture-based tasks teaching/learning in integration.

Factors and challenges related to the school such as shortage of teaching aid equipment, unsuitable seating for group work in the classroom, large class size, lack of in-service adequate training on integrate skill teaching. Besides, challenges related students such as lack of basic skill of spoken skills, lack of linguistic skills, the inability of using oral skills in their real-life situation, poor background knowledge, poor participation, and lack of practicing writing skill, problem of arranging ideas in sequence and logical way and preference of translation to mother tongue. Similarly, factors/challenges related to ELT namely, lack of adequate training on how practically teach writing with reading skill teaching in integration, inability to design additional material, lack of motivation and inability to act their managerial role are challenges negatively teaching writing with reading skill in integration.

On the basis of the major findings of the current research ,recommendations are made to policy makers ,syllabus designers ,school teachers ,and curriculum designers in that of the teaching of culture-based activities is undeniably to promote learners oral skills in the EFL classrooms ; the principle involves the cultivation of cultural awareness and the approaches to develop cultural awareness, aims at a tentative exploration into the modern teaching method of foreign language teaching; attention should be given that culture-based tasks are crucial in foreign language teaching cannot be so overemphasized as to neglect the teaching of linguistic knowledge ;as part of this pedagogical requirement is serious regular preparation for classes by teachers and students ;and teachers should identify the problems during the implementation of intercultural oriented task-based instruction and provide students dialectical thinking space allow the students to realize that cross-cultural communication is not to give up their own culture to follow or go along with the other party's cultural practices.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares that there is no conflict of interests.

About the Author

The author, a PhD Scholar, has been teaching English as foreign language at preparatory Level for over 8 years. After years of English language teaching, He has come to attend PhD program at Jimma University to specialize English as a foreign language.

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Appendix 1: Questionnaire to be filled by Learners

Part One: Personal information of the respondents

Instruction: Please give the required information about yourself by putting a tick mark (√) or by writing down the required information on the blank space given against each them.

1. Sex: 1.1/ Male: -----, 1.2/ Female: -----, 2/Year-----, 3/College-----

4. /Age: -----, and 5/ Date-----, 6: Group Code-----

Part Two: Close-ended Part of the Questionnaire

Key for the Five Point Rating Scale

Key: 1: Strongly disagree, 2: Disagree, 3: Neither disagree nor agree, 4: Agree, 5: Strongly agree

Instruction: Put a tick mark (√) in the appropriate box in front of each item based on the following rating scales.

Challenges/Problems/	Rating Scales				
	1	2	3	4	5
1. Teacher Related Challenges					
1.1. The teacher's lack of knowledge and experience in preparing intercultural communication based tasks that intend to develop learners' oral skills.	1	2	3	4	5
1.2. Lack of appropriately prepared or adopted authentic intercultural oriented learning material for meeting the demands of effective interaction in the Spoken language classroom.	1	2	3	4	5
1.3. Lack of using new or innovative teaching techniques during the Oral lessons offered.	1	2	3	4	5
1.4. Use of teacher-cantered teaching methods during the speaking Lessons.	1	2	3	4	5
1.5. Lack of various intercultural communication oriented task based activities in the spoken lessons.	1	2	3	4	5
1.6. Failure in giving clear instruction.	1	2	3	4	5

1.7. Lack of enough guide and support to learners when they face problems in doing intercultural communication oriented task based speaking activities	1	2	3	4	5
1.8. Use of difficult English in the speaking instruction.	1	2	3	4	5
1.9. Lack of encouraging learners to take part in the speaking tasks.	1	2	3	4	5
1.10. Lack of good or effective classrooms management.	1	2	3	4	5
1.11. No objectives set for the spoken lesson.	1	2	3	4	5
2.Trainees Related Challenges	1	2	3	4	5
2.1. I lack background or prior knowledge and experiences of doing Such speaking or oral tasks at lower learning levels.	1	2	3	4	5
2.2. I Lack basic English language skills for doing intercultural communication oriented task based that intends to improve Speaking activities.	1	2	3	4	5
2.3. My fear of making mistakes, losing face, criticism, and my Shyness during task-based speaking instruction.	1	2	3	4	5
2.4. Poor vocabulary Knowledge in English Language	1	2	3	4	5
2.5. I Lack motivation to learn through such tasks that were used in the oral lessons.	1	2	3	4	5
2.6. I prefer to use my mother tongue during English speaking lessons.	1	2	3	4	5
2.7. Lack of confidence in taking part in the intercultural communication oriented task based English Spoken lessons.	1	2	3	4	5
2.8. Speaking in English is difficult for me.	1	2	3	4	5
2.9.Hating interactive pair or group works during the spoken lessons.	1	2	3	4	5
3.Learning Resources and Environment Related Challenges	1	2	3	4	5
3.1. Enough time is not given for the teaching and learning intercultural communication oriented tasks that intend to promote student's Spoken skills.	1	2	3	4	5
3.2. Lack of appropriate teaching aids to facilitate the English speaking lessons.	1	2	3	4	5

3.3 Lack of adequate or enough teaching aids to facilitate the English speaking lessons.	1	2	3	4	5
3.4 The sitting arrangements (or, the seats) are not convenient for interactive group works that facilitate learners English speaking skills.	1	2	3	4	5
3.5. English language is not spoken outside classrooms.	1	2	3	4	5
3.6.Shortage of time allotted to different task based activities to Promote learners' oral skills development.	1	2	3	4	5
3.7 The classroom surrounding is noisy.	1	2	3	4	5

Part Three: Open-ended Item

If you have any more ideas or comments about the major challenges you faced in the oral lessons, write down here.-----

Thank you for your cooperation!

The Researcher